

INVESTIGATIONS ON ISOTOPIC ELEMENTS IN TERMS OF QUARKS

Arpan Dey

ABSTRACT

Isotopes of an element have the same atomic number but different atomic masses. Although it is most convenient to talk about isotopes in terms of protons and neutrons, it may be interesting to think of isotopes in terms of quarks. Quarks are the particles that make up the protons and neutrons, which constitute the nucleus of an atom. Quarks can be of different types: up, down, charm, strange, bottom, and top. Among them, only up and down quarks are stable enough to form protons and neutrons. Thus, in the study of isotopes, we must confine ourselves to up and down quarks. In this article, some relations regarding the number of up and down quarks for isotopic elements are determined. After evaluating the elements of the periodic table based on the number of up and down quarks in their nuclei, the case of isotopes was considered and certain relations were determined for different types of isotopic elements. The formulae were then verified for different elements, with lower as well as higher atomic masses.

INTRODUCTION

Elements are ultimately made up of atoms, which in turn, consist of a nucleus and individual electrons revolving around the nucleus. The quark is an essential fundamental particle in the Standard Model which (the latter) attempts to explain the fundamental forces of nature (except gravity) in terms of particles, that is, either fermions or bosons. The fermion constitutes physical matter, while the exchange of the boson gives rise to forces between particles. The electron is a fermion. Fermions can be divided into two groups: quarks and leptons. Leptons are weakly-interacting particles (particles that interact using the weak nuclear force), for example, electrons. The nucleus, made up of protons and neutrons, is comparatively massive and lies at the center of the atom. Protons are made up of two up quarks and one down quark. Neutrons, which are chargeless particles, have two down quarks and one up quark. (It should be noted that quark-antiquark pairs may be present in the protons or neutrons. The antiquark is the antiparticle of the quark. It has similar properties but is oppositely-charged. Being equally and oppositely-charged, quark-antiquark pairs do not affect the overall charge of the protons or neutrons.)

Atoms are neutral, that is, they have equal amounts of positive and negative charges. This is because the electrons are negatively charged, while the protons have a charge equal in magnitude to that of the electron but positive in nature. The number of protons and electrons are equal in a neutral atom. When this does not hold, an ion is formed, which can be positively-charged (cation) or negatively-charged (anion). Here, however, the discussion is regarding isotopes of neutral atoms.

The neutron is a chargeless particle because the relative charge of an up quark is positive two-thirds the charge of an electron, i.e, $2/3$ units; while the relative charge of a down quark is negative one-third the charge of an electron that is, $-1/3$ units. The combination of two up and one down quark in a proton will have a relative charge of positive one unit [$2(2/3) + (-1/3) = 4/3 - 1/3 = 3/3 = 1$], while it will be zero for a neutron (that is, two down and one up quark). Isotopes of an element have atoms that have equal numbers of protons and electrons but excess neutrons, which affects the mass but not the charge. The mass of the isotope may exceed the original mass of the

element by one atomic mass unit, two units or more. Most elements with lower atomic numbers (or masses) have an atomic mass approximately equal to twice the atomic number. This is because the atomic number is just the number of protons or, in case of a neutral atom, the number of electrons. The mass number is just the sum of the number of protons and the number of neutrons (electrons have almost no mass). It must be noted that the isotopes of an element are found in different quantities in nature. The abundance percentage of an isotope defines what percentage of that isotope constitute all isotopes of that element in nature.

METHODS

The methods used to arrive at the results have been discussed here.

1. Ignoring quark-antiquark pairs, a proton consists of two up and one down quark. Thus, it can be represented as $2u\ 1d$. Similarly, a neutron has 2 down and 1 up quark, that is, $2d\ 1u$.
2. Isotopes, generally, have more neutrons than protons. This is because, as long as the isotopes are of the same element, their atomic number, and hence, the number of protons, remains the same. Thus, although there are certain exceptions, heavier isotopes usually have more down quarks than up quarks, since neutrons contain more down quarks than up.
3. The difference between the mass number of the heavier isotope and the average atomic mass of that element, when all its isotopes are considered (if, and only if the average atomic mass has been calculated by taking into account the abundance percentages), added to the difference between the number of up and down quarks, also calculated by taking into account the abundance percentages, must always be a whole number, other than zero. Also, the difference between the mass number of the heavier isotope and the average atomic mass of that element, cannot be zero if the element has isotopes. [Let A and B be the lighter and heavier isotopes, respectively, and let C be the average atomic mass of that element. If $(B - C) = 0$, $B = C$, which indicates that the given element has no isotopes. This is because B can be equal to C when, and only when, one isotope is 100% abundant and the other (say, A) is 0% abundant. In that case, $C = 0/100 \times A + 100/100 \times B = 0 + B = B$.]
4. For an efficient approach to the issue, isotopic elements can be divided into three "classes": Class 1 elements, Class 2 elements, and Class 3 elements.
5. Class 1 elements are elements with two naturally-occurring isotopes such that:
 - (i) The mass number of the lighter isotope is exactly twice the atomic number of the element.
 - (ii) The difference between the mass numbers of the isotopes is exactly 1 atomic mass unit, that is, the heavier isotope is heavier than the lighter one by 1 atomic mass unit.
6. Class 2 elements are elements with two naturally-occurring isotopes such that:
 - (i) The mass number of an isotope is NOT twice the atomic number of that element.
 - (ii) The difference between the mass numbers of the isotopes is 1 atomic mass unit, i.e., the heavier isotope is heavier than the lighter one by 1 atomic mass unit.
7. Class 3 elements are elements with two naturally-occurring isotopes such that:
 - (i) The mass number of an isotope is not necessarily twice the atomic number of that element.
 - (ii) The difference between the mass numbers of the isotopes is greater than 1 atomic mass unit.
8. At certain points in the calculations, numbers have been rounded up to two, three or

four decimal places, as convenient. For instance, 2.788692213... can be rounded up to 2.79, and so on. Also, the abundance percentages of isotopes can be rounded up similarly as convenient. However, this must satisfy that the sum of the percentage abundance of all the isotopes of that element equals 100.

9. For elements having more than 2 naturally-occurring isotopes (say, b elements, that is, it can be a Class 1- b element, a Class 2- b element, or a Class 3- b element), any 2 isotopes can be taken into account. Taking into account their abundance percentages (when all the isotopes are considered) and the sum of abundance percentages of these 2 isotopes, their abundance percentages can be modified such that only these 2 isotopes are present, of that element. (This is just being done to test the formula for such cases, for it is not physically valid to “eliminate” the other isotopes.) In such cases, values extremely close to a whole number, but not exactly a whole number, tend to arise.
10. Considering the abundance percentages of the isotopes and their respective masses, the average atomic mass of the element was found using known methods. [At this point, it should be noted that many elements may have many isotopes, but few of them are stable. In this paper, only the stable isotopes are of relevance and thus, only they have been taken into account. For instance, Lithium has more than two isotopes. However, only two of them, Lithium-6 and Lithium-7, are stable.]
11. After that, the difference between the mass number of the heavier isotope and the average atomic mass of that element was considered. Let an element have two isotopes, A and B such that B is heavier than A. Let C be the average atomic mass. Then, first $(B - C)$ was considered. Then, the difference between the *total* number of down and up quarks in a single atom of that element (taking into consideration their abundance percentages in nature) was considered, that is, say $(d - u)$. Finally, the expression $(B - C) + (d - u)$ was considered for Classes 1, 2 and 3 elements. This is explained clearly with examples under the “Calculations” section.

POSTULATES

1. For neutral atoms, arranged in the order of increasing atomic number, with the exception of hydrogen, the number of up as well as down quarks in the nucleus increase by 3, for every element. (There may be certain exceptions to this rule.)
2. Without considering hydrogen, the number of up quarks in an element (that is to say, in a single atom of that element) cannot exceed the number of down quarks for the same element. (There are exceptions to this rule, but it holds in most cases. For instance, Helium-3, which is a stable isotope, has 2 protons and 1 neutron, that is, 5 up quarks and 4 down quarks.)
3. For isotopic elements, if x up and y down represent the total number of up and down quarks in a single atom of one isotope of that element; and a up and b down represent the same for the heavier isotope, $a = x + (1m)$ and $b = y + (2m)$, where m is the difference between the mass numbers of the two (or more) isotopes.
4. For Class 1 elements, $n - p = (d - u)$, where $(n - p)$ is the difference between the total number of neutrons and protons in one atom of both the isotopes.
5. For Class 1 elements, $|p_1 - p_2| + |n_1 - n_2| = (d - u)$, where the Left-Hand Side of the equation represents the sum of the modulus (that is, only the magnitude) of the difference between the number of protons and that of neutrons (without taking into account abundance percentages) for both the isotopes.
6. For Class 1 elements, $(B - C) + (d - u) = 1$.

7. For Class 2 elements, $(B - C) + (d - u) = n$, where n is some whole number other than 0. More generally, this may be written as: (for Class 2 elements) $(B - C) + (d - u) = 1 + z$, where z = the number by which the lighter isotope's atomic mass is more than twice the atomic number of that element. This is explained under the "Calculations" section.
8. For Class 3 elements as well, $(B - C) + (d - u) = n$, where n is a whole number other than 0.
9. It is also evident that $C - (d - u) = 2Z$, where Z is the atomic number of the element. From the following calculations, it would be clear that the expression after the decimal point of the average atomic mass of an element C , and the expression after the decimal point of $(d - u)$ are the same; and their difference yields a number which is twice the atomic number of the element in question. If the element in question has an isotope whose mass is exactly twice the atomic number, then $C - (d - u)$ would equal the mass of that isotope, usually the lighter isotope. (It should be noted that the lightest possible atomic mass of any element cannot be less than twice the atomic number, since the number of neutrons, usually, is NOT less than the number of protons. However, there are some exceptions like protium, Helium-3 etc..)

CALCULATIONS

1. The first calculation verifies the formula established under point 3 of the "Postulates" section. Sulphur has 4 isotopes with mass numbers 32, 33, 34, and 36. In S-32, we have 16 neutrons(n^0), 16 protons(p^+) and 16 electrons(e^-). As one neutron has 2 down and 1 up quarks, 16 neutrons will have $(16 \times 2)d$ and 16u quarks, that is, 32d 16u. Each proton has 2 up and 1 down quark, that is, 32u 16d for 16 protons. Thus, we have a total of 48u 48d. Here, $x = 48$, $y = 48$. Similarly, it is 49u 50d for S-33, that is, $(x + 1m)u (y + 2m)d = (48 + 1)u (48 + 2)d$. It is of importance, here, that m , that is, the difference between the mass numbers, is $33 - 32 = 1$. It is 50u 52d for S-34. For S-36, when S-34 and S-36 are considered, $m = 2$. Thus, au bd is $(50 + 2)u (52 + 4)d = 52u 56d$. One might choose to consider S-32 and S-36, in which case, $m = 4$. Thus, au bd is $(48 + 4)u (48 + 8)d = 52u 56d$. This can be verified for other isotopes as well.
2. The following calculations verify the formula presented under point 8 of the "Postulates" section. Lithium has atomic number 3 and 2 isotopes of mass numbers 6 (that is, 3×2) and 7. [$7 - 6 = 1$] Thus, Lithium can be considered a Class 1 element, as per the convention presented under the "Methods" section. The average atomic mass of Lithium, taking into account abundance percentages is 6.925 units. Lithium-6 accounts for approximately 7.5% of all the Lithium available, while 92.5% of it is Lithium-7. Thus, the average atomic mass: $7.5 \times 6/100 + 92.5 \times 7/100 = 0.45 + 6.475 = 6.925$. Here, $(B - C) = 7 - 6.925 = 0.075$ (i)

Li-6	Li-7
Neutrons: 6 - 3 = 3	Neutrons: 7 - 3 = 4 (atomic mass is always 3)
Protons: 3	Protons: 3
6d 3u	8d 4u
+ 6u 3d	+ 6u 3d
= 9u 9d	= 10u 11d

Considering the fact that 7.5% Lithium is Li-6 and the rest is Li-7, we get: $7.5 \times 9/100u$ $7.5 \times 9/100d$ and $92.5 \times 10/100u$ $92.5 \times 11/100d = 0.675u$ $0.675d$ and $9.25u$ $10.175d = 9.925u$ $10.85d$ (adding up the total number of up and down quarks obtained in the previous step.) Thus, $d - u = 10.85 - 9.925 = 0.925$ (ii)

From (i) and (ii), $(B - C) + (d - u) = 0.075 + 0.925 = 1$.

Boron (atomic number 5) has 2 isotopes of mass numbers 10 (that is, 5×2) [20%] and 11 [80%]. Proceeding in a similar way, it is observed that the average atomic mass of Boron is 10.8 units. Thus, $(B - C) = 11 - 10.8 = 0.2$. For Boron-10, we get $15u$ $15d$; and for Boron-11, we get $16u$ $17d$. Considering the abundance percentages, we get $3u$ $3d$ and $12.8u$ $13.6d$. Taking the sum of the up and down quarks, the final result is $16.6d$ $15.8u$. $(d - u) = 16.6 - 15.8 = 0.8$. Thus, it is clear that $(B - C) + (d - u) = 0.2 + 0.8 = 1$.

For Carbon (atomic number 6), there are 2 isotopes, C-12 [99%] and C-13 [1%]. $C = 99 \times 12/100 + 1 \times 13/100 = 11.88 + 0.13 = 12.01$. $(B - C) = 13 - 12.01 = 0.99$. The number of up and down quarks, before considering the abundance percentages, is $18u$ $18d$ for C-12 and $19u$ $20d$ for C-13. This can easily be predicted from previous formulae. Taking into account the abundance percentages, the result is $17.82u$ $17.82d$ and $0.19u$ $0.20d$. On adding the up and down quarks, the final result is $18.02d$ and $18.01u$. Thus, $(d - u) = 18.02 - 18.01 = 0.01$. $(B - C) + (d - u) = 0.99 + 0.01 = 1$.

For Nitrogen (atomic number 6), there are 2 isotopes, N-14 [99.6%] and N-15 [0.4%]. $C = 99.6 \times 14/100 + 0.4 \times 15/100 = 13.944 + 0.06 = 14.004$. $(B - C) = 15 - 14.004 = 0.996$. The number of up and down quarks, before considering the abundance percentages, is $21u$ $21d$ for N-14 and $22u$ $23d$ for N-15. Taking into account the abundance percentages, the result is $20.916u$ $20.916d$ and $0.088u$ $0.092d$. On adding the up and down quarks, the final result is $21.008d$ and $21.004u$. Thus, $(d - u) = 21.008 - 21.004 = 0.004$. $(B - C) + (d - u) = 0.996 + 0.004 = 1$. From the above examples, it is evident that $(B - C)$ and $(d - u)$ are always the abundance percentages of both the isotopes divided by 100, at least for this class of elements. For instance, in the case of Nitrogen, the abundance percentages of N-14 and N-15, respectively, are 99.6% and 0.4%. And $(B - C) = 99.6/100 = 0.996$. And $(d - u) = 0.4/100 = 0.004$.

3. The following calculation verifies the formula presented under point 9 of the "Results" section. The element Vanadium, with atomic number 23 but 2 isotopes with mass numbers 50 (that is, 23×2) [0.25%] and 51 (that is, 23×2) [99.75%], $(B - C) = 51 - 50.9975 = 0.0025$; while $(d - u) = 78.995 - 73.9975 = 4.9975$. Thus, $(B - C) + (d - u) = 0.0025 + 4.9975 = 5$, which is a whole number other than 0. It must be stressed that in the above example, the result would have been 1 if the atomic mass of one isotope (that is, lighter isotope) was $23 \times 2 = 46$. But the mass number of the lighter isotope is $46 + 4 = 50$. Thus, we could have easily predicted that $(B - C) + (d - u)$ would be $1 + 4 = 5$.
4. The following calculations verify the formula presented under point 10 of the "Postulates" section. For Chlorine (atomic number 17), there are 2 isotopes Cl-35 (that is, 17×2) [75%] and Cl-37 [25%]. The average atomic mass is 35.5 units. Here, $(B - C) = 37 - 35.5 = 1.5$ and $(d - u)$ comes out to be $54 - 52.5 = 1.5$. Thus, $(B - C) + (d - u) = 1.5 + 1.5 = 3$, which is a whole number. For Argon (atomic number 18), there are 3 isotopes: Argon-36 [0.3%], Argon-38 [0.1%] and Argon-40 [99.6%]. If only Argon-36 and -38 are considered, a modified abundance percentage of Argon-36 would be: $0.3/(0.3+0.1) \times 100 = 75\%$. This is because the abundance percentage of Argon-36, when all the isotopes are considered, is 0.3%. Similarly, the abundance percentage of Argon-38, when all the isotopes are considered, is 0.1% (the numerator). When only these isotopes are considered, the total abundance becomes $0.3 + 0.1$ (which thus becomes the denominator) and the percentage abundance for Argon-36, would then be, 75%, as shown above. This result can be achieved by multiplying the fraction by 100. Similarly, in this case, an abundance percentage for Argon-38 would be 25% ($= 100 - 75$).

Here, the average atomic mass is 36.5 units. Thus, $(B - C) = 38 - 36.5 = 1.5$. And, in this case, $(d - u) = 55 - 54.5 = 0.5$. Thus, $(B - C) + (d - u) = 1.5 + 0.5 = 2$, which is a whole number. Similarly, for Argon-36 and Argon-40, we get, $(B - U) = 40 - 39.984 = 0.016$ and $(d - u) = 61.968 - 57.984 = 3.984$. Thus, $(B - C) + (d - u) = 0.016 + 3.984 = 4$, which is a whole number. It is interesting, at this point, to consider the case of Potassium (atomic number 19), which has 3 isotopes of mass numbers 39 [93.26%], 40 [0.01%], and 41 [6.73%] (approximately). Proceeding as in the case of Argon, Potassium-39 and -40 can be considered. The abundance percentages will, respectively for K-39 and K-40, be 99.99% and 0.01%. Using these values, it is observed that the average atomic mass, when ONLY these 2 isotopes of Potassium are considered, is 39.0001 units. $(B - C) = 40 - 39.0001 = 0.9999$. $(d - u) = 59.0002 - 58.0001 = 1.0001$. Hence, $(B - C) + (d - u) = 0.9999 + 1.0001 = 2$, which is a whole number. By now, a clear understanding of the process that is being used to obtain the values for $(B - C)$ and $(d - u)$ is attainable. Thus, only these values for the following elements have been provided. For K-39 and K-41, after modifying the abundance percentages, $(B - C) + (d - u) = 1.8654 + 1.1346 = 3$, which is a whole number. For K-40 and K-41, after modifying the abundance percentages, $(B - C) + (d - u) = 0.0015 + 2.9985 = 3$, which is a whole number. Sulphur (atomic number 16) has 4 isotopes of mass numbers 32 [95.02%], 33 [0.75%], 34 [4.21%], and 36 [0.02%]. For S-32 and S-33, $(B - C) + (d - u) = 0.9922 + 0.0078 = 1$, which is a whole number. For S-32 and S-34, $(B - C) + (d - u) = 1.9152 + 0.0848 = 2$, which is a whole number. For S-32 and S-36, $(B - C) + (d - u) = 3.9992 + 0.0008 = 4$, which is a whole number. For S-33 and S-34, $(B - C) + (d - u) = 0.1512 + 1.8488 = 2$, which is a whole number. For S-33 and S-36, $(B - C) + (d - u) = 2.922 + 1.078 = 4$, which is a whole number. For S-34 and S-36, $(B - C) + (d - u) = 1.9906 + 2.0094 = 4$, which is a whole number. Copper (atomic number 29) has 2 isotopes: Cu-63 [69%] and Cu-65 [31%]. For Copper, $(B - C) + (d - u) = (65 - 63.62) + (98.24 - 92.62) = 1.38 + 5.62 = 7$, which is a whole number. Finally, the case of a much heavier element, Uranium (atomic number 92) and its 2 main isotopes, U-235 [0.7%] and U-238 [99.3%] can be considered. In this case, $(B - C) = 238 - 237.979 = 0.021$.

Uranium-235	Uranium-238
Neutrons: 235 - 92 = 143	Neutrons: 238 - 92 = 146
Protons: 92	Protons: 92
(143 X 2)d 143u	(146 X 2)d 146u
(92 X 2)u 92d	(92 X 2)u 92d
327u 378d	330u 384d

$= 0.7 \times 327/100u + 0.7 \times 378/100d$ and $99.3 \times 330/100u + 99.3 \times 384/100d = 2.289u + 2.646d$ and $330u + 384d = 329.979u + 383.958d$. $(d - u) = 383.958 - 329.979 = 53.979$. Hence, $(B - C) + (d - u) = 0.021 + 53.979 = 54$, which is a whole number. We have seen that: For Class 2 elements, $(B -$

$C) + (d - u) = 1 + z$, where z = the number by which the lighter isotope's atomic mass is more than twice the atomic number of that element. If the case of Uranium is considered more closely, it is evident that $(B - C) + (d - u)$ equals $1 + z + \{(B - A) - 1\}$. Thus, the formula obtained in the case of Vanadium was only a special case. In the case of Vanadium, $(B - A) =$ difference between the mass numbers of the 2 isotopes = $51 - 50 = 1$. Thus, $\{(B - A) - 1\}$ is $1 - 1 = 0$. In the cases where the isotopes differ by a mass of 1 unit, $(B - C) + (d - u) = 1 + z$, would work. But the general formula to directly obtain the result of $(B - C) + (d - u)$, thus, for 2 isotopes of mass numbers A and B , $A < B$, with average atomic mass, C , and $z = (A - 2Z)$, where Z = the atomic number of that element is: $(B - C) + (d - u) = 1 + z + B - A - 1 = z + (B - A)$. It may also be written in this form: $(d - u) = z + (C - A)$. This formula directly predicts the value of $(d - u)$ if z , C and A are known, and can be of importance in certain cases. This formula is far more general than anything achieved so far. The above formula can be verified for ALL the cases considered, and, if possible, even beyond. For instance, in the case of Lithium, $(d - u)$ was 0.925. The average atomic mass C was 6.925. A , or the mass of the lighter isotope is clearly 6. Atomic number of Lithium, $Z = 3$. Thus, $z = A - 2Z = 6 - 2(3) = 6 - 6 = 0$. $Z + (C - A) = 0 + (6.925 - 6) = 0.925 = (d - u)$. For elements with the mass number of one isotope precisely equal to twice the atomic number, the formula collapses to $(B - A)$. Even for elements such as Sulphur, in which cases different combinations of 2 isotopes have been considered, the formula works after modifying the abundance percentages.

DISCUSSION

No particular work has been done specifically addressing isotopic elements in terms of the number of up and down quarks. Isotopes are usually studied under chemistry, and the relation of isotopes with quarks is not direct. However, the results and calculations suggest that certain relations can be established for isotopic elements, in terms of the number of up/down quarks, the atomic number of that element, etc..

CONCLUSION

It has been verified that the mass of the lighter isotope subtracted from the average atomic mass of an element (by considering abundance percentages and by considering only two isotopes at a time), added to the number by which the lighter isotope's atomic mass is more than twice the atomic number of the element, equals the total number of up quarks subtracted from the total number of down quarks, of both the isotopes (by taking in account the abundance percentages). Concludingly, it should be noted that it is in itself obvious why the number of neutrons should be greater than the number of protons for most elements: to compensate for the forces of repulsion due to so many like-charged protons confined in a small nucleus, and keep the nucleus stable. The main point of this paper was to determine certain relations regarding isotopic elements in terms of up and down quarks. Though the relations seem to hold, they do not have any direct applications.